

DATABASE/RISK MANAGEMENT COMPETENCIES REQUIRED OF OFFICE TECHNOLOGY AND MANAGEMENT (OTM) GRADUATES OF POLYTECHNICS IN GOMBE STATE, NIGERIA FOR ELECTRONIC RECORDS MANAGEMENT

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Abstract: This study ascertained database and risk management competencies required of polytechnic OTM graduates in Gombe State, Nigeria for electronic records management. Two research questions and four null hypotheses guided the study. The study adopted survey research design, and 66 administrative supervisors were studied without sampling. A Self-developed questionnaire with 25 items which was face validated by experts in Business Education and Measurement and Evaluation were used for data collection. The reliability of the instrument was determined using pilot testing and data calculated analyzed using Cronbach Alpha formula which yielded correlation values of .91 and .85 for clusters B1 to B2 respectively with an overall reliability value of .88. Mean, standard deviation, ANOVA and t-test were used for data analysis. Findings showed that database management competencies, and risk management competencies were highly required of OTM graduates of polytechnics in Gombe State, Nigeria for electronic records management. Years of experience and educational attainment were not significant factors in the mean ratings of respondents on the extent database management competencies were required of OTM graduates of polytechnics for electronic records management. However, while years of experience did not moderate risk management skills, educational attainment moderated respondents' opinions in this regard. Based on the findings of the study, the researchers concluded that; OTM graduates in polytechnics in Gombe State, Nigeria highly required database and risk management competencies for effective management of the institutions' records. It was recommended that administrators of Nigerian polytechnics should constantly re-train OTM graduates working in their institutions by providing in-service programmes such as workshops, seminars and conferences to enable them up-date their database and risks management competencies for effective records management

Keywords: Database Management Competencies, Risk Management Competencies, OTM, Electronic Records Management.

1. INTRODUCTION

Polytechnic education is acknowledged globally as a crucial part of the education system because it trains young people in technical and non-technical competencies they need to contribute to the development of their countries. In Nigeria, polytechnics were established particularly to train and prepare students for the workplace. In addition to the broad objectives

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of tertiary education in No. 59, the National Policy on Education, as quoted in Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN, 2013), stipulates in No. 80 that polytechnics shall among other strain students on skills needed to become technicians, technologists, and or job creators. One of the programmes offered in polytechnics is Office Technology and Management (OTM) which is seen as an effective educational programme that encourages independence. The goal of OTM is to equip students with knowledge and skills for gainful employment or self-employment (Nnaji, 2019). OTM programme according to Orija and Jolaade (2019) is work-oriented in nature, and its graduates can fit into millennium workplaces thanks to trainings received while in school. The National Board for Technical Education (NBTE, 2009) observed that the OTM curriculum incorporates computer-related courses in ICT applications (computer usage such as web page design, desktop publishing, and database management) in addition to general education courses. The OTM programme is under growing pressure to produce graduates with appropriate competencies to fit into the current labour market. The programme trains students in various competencies in order to close the prevalent competency gaps that contribute to high unemployment rate among graduates. Some of these competencies according to Mehrotra and Elias (2017) are good communication, time-management, interpersonal, and records management competencies.

Records are information that has been officially recorded which may take the shape of a physical object or digital data. All forms of certificates and official documents are examples of tangible records, whereas digital records include emails, x-rays, and other types of digital data (Nyampong, 2015). In tertiary institutions (polytechnics inclusive), records are official documents, books and files containing crucial information of actions and events preserved in offices for retrieval and use when needed (Amanchukwu & Ololube, 2015). Records in polytechnics must be effectively managed to prevent unauthorized access, damage, or tampering that affect the polytechnics' privacy and accountability. Indeed, the survival and image of polytechnics suffer when their records are not complete, objective, available, and accessible.

Records management describes a methodical approach to managing the lifespan of records that are regularly produced as a result of transactions and activities. Ugwu, Onoh, and Chikwe (2018) stated that records management involves managing all records, whether printed or in digital form, from the time of creation until they are disposed of. The goal of records management is to help polytechnics keep necessary documentation accessible for both educational operations and compliance audits. Polytechnics in the past handled their records the old-fashioned way, which involved storing large volumes of hard copies of documents in filing cabinets. However, this system is no longer effective due to the huge amount of records being created daily by the polytechnics. Hence, many polytechnics in Nigeria are adopting electronic records management systems.

Electronic records can reside in a general electronic information system or be created with a software such as word processing (text files) or e-mail and are not always kept in a "record keeping system" (United National Archives and Records Administration, 2019). Text files (files created by word processors), data files (computer processable), and analogue audio and visual records (sound documents and images) are the three main types of e-records. To maintain polytechnic documents electronically, the OTM programme graduates may need to possess a variety of competencies such as physical filing competencies, record life cycle competencies, and Computer Assisted Retrieval (CAR) competencies. Similarly, OTM graduates could also possess cloud computing, e-mail record competencies (Kibe, 2016), as well as word processing competencies, database management competencies, records organization, records planning, and records disposal competencies (Okolocha & Baba, 2017; Ovbiagele, Mgbonyebi & Olaniye, 2019) This study considered competencies related to database/risk management.

Database is the key bank of information of every educational institution. Database is a collection of information (both alphabetic and numerical) stored in organized manner. Database management competencies are taught in OTM programme and include; ability to extract and list all records, follow data entry and normalization conventions, interpret quality control procedures when analyzing data quality and analyzing data quality to identify discrepancies (Dietrich, 2017). Other database management competencies according to Nwachukwu (2015) are abilities to: retrieve desired information instantly and in the desired format, store data in a secure manner to guide against unauthorized access, and maintain data stored in the database. In performing database management tasks, OTM graduates need to be aware of the potential risks of data/records damage or loss. Therefore, potential secretaries (OTM graduates) should be able to identify potential risks to polytechnics' records, anticipate and mitigate potential data damages or losses; and control unauthorized access to records. Dietrich (2017) listed risk management competencies as abilities to carry out records risk analysis, recover data and perform regular data auditing. Others are ability to conduct risk assessment that examines known or anticipated risk to records, and ability to systematically control the level of risk exposure of an organization.

Risk in simple terms means the possibility of something bad happening. Risk involves uncertainty about the effects/implications of an activity with respect to something that humans value (such as health, well-being, wealth, property or the environment), often focusing on negative, undesirable consequences. It relates to the effect of uncertainty on objectives. Verma (2022) views it as the chances of having an unexpected or negative outcome. Verma stated that any action or activity that leads to loss of any type can be termed as risk.

Risk can be categorized into financial risk, physical risk, business risk, and intellectual risk (Hay-Gibson, 2012). Financial risk is the risk that involves financial loss to organizations. It arises due to instability and losses in the financial market caused by movements in stock prices, currencies, interest rates and more (Verma, 2022). Financial risk is one of the high-priority risk types for every organization (polytechnics inclusive). It is caused due to market movements and market movements. Types of financial risk are market risk, credit risk, liquidity risk, operational risk, and legal risk (Verma, 2022). Market risk arises due to the movement in prices of financial instrument. It can be directional and non-directional. Directional risk is caused due to movement in stock price, interest rates and more. Non-directional risk is caused by volatility of markets. Credit risk arises when an organization fails to fulfill its obligations towards counterparties. This risk can be sovereign risk and settlement risk. Sovereign risk usually arises due to difficult foreign exchange policies. Settlement risk arises when one party makes the payment while the other party fails to fulfill the obligations (Verma, 2022).

In Nigeria, students seek admission into polytechnic OTM programme with the expectation that on graduation, they would have acquired relevant competencies to work as professionals in their field. Competencies employers demand from OTM graduates are constantly changing in line with changes in information technology (IT). Crowne (2019) stated that one concern employers in Nigeria have is the nature of competencies OTM graduates are taught while in school. This concern is given renewed focus in the face of high rate of unemployment among OTM graduates. These concerns underscore the need for regular assessment of electronic competencies polytechnic OTM graduates require for effective record management. According to an observation by Okolocha and Baba (2017), most secretaries (OTM graduate workers inclusive) from polytechnics still find it difficult to effectively manage records using the electronic system.

This scenario could also be a concern for administrators as well as administrative supervisors in polytechnics in Nigeria. As noted by Gude (2020), administrative supervisors in tertiary institutions guide, direct and manage the job tasks of junior staff in the workplace to achieve institutional goals. By the nature of their duties, they control workers in charge of record keeping, and their knowledge and responsibilities qualify them to assess competencies required of polytechnic OTM graduates for electronic records management.

Work experience could play a very key role in database and risks management in educational institutions. Work experience could help administrative supervisors determine the best database and risks management competencies required of OTM graduates. It is likely that the opinions of administrative supervisors with above 10 years of experience will vary from those with 6–10 years on electronic records management competencies required of polytechnic OTM graduates while those with 6–10 years will differ from those with 1-5 years in this regard. This could be attributed to differences in training and other experiences which may lead to the acquisition of different competencies. Similarly, administrative supervisors may differ in their perception of database management competencies required of OTM graduates based on their educational attainment. Supervisors with higher degrees (PhD/M.Sc) may differ with those with lower degrees (B.Sc/B.Ed/HND) in this regard. This could be attributed to exposure to different electronic records management competencies during course of learning. Amesi (2014) in support asserted that educational attainment makes successful managers/administrators to acquire more competencies. The rate at which polytechnics' records are lost or damaged which affect decision making and ability to assess progress raises a question of database/risk management competencies OTM graduates in polytechnics in Gombe State, Nigeria require for electronic records management.

Statement of the Problem

Records are the livewire of any tertiary educational institution as adequate records management provides good information for management to make informed decisions. The OTM programme in polytechnics recognizes the importance of equipping students with records management competencies and has incorporated courses that teach record management in its curriculum. Hence, every OTM graduate is expected to possess relevant competencies for effective records management. The advent of technologies in records management system has led to new competencies emerging while old competencies have fizzled out. This demands that polytechnic OTM graduates need other competencies in order to adequately manage records.

Presently, employers of labour are dissatisfied with the quality of OTM graduates who they claim find it difficult to effectively manage records electronically. OTM graduate workers in Nigerian polytechnics do not possess relevant electronic competencies for effective performance. Similarly, an observation by the researcher showed that some OTM graduates from polytechnics in Gombe State, Nigeria are unemployed while some who manage to be employed in administrative jobs perform below employers' expectations. This scenario could be attributed to a mismatch between records management competencies they were exposed to, and the competencies employers of labour require of them for records management in the digital age. In view of this, the OTM curriculum seems inadequate in equipping students with electronic records management competencies for office management jobs upon graduation. Therefore, this study specifically ascertained the extent (a) database management competencies are required of OTM graduates of polytechnics in Gombe State, Nigeria for electronic records management (b) records risk management competencies are required of OTM graduates of polytechnics in Gombe and Bauchi States, Nigeria for electronic records management.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study;

1. To what extent are database management competencies required of OTM graduates of polytechnics in Gombe State, Nigeria for electronic records management?
2. To what extent are risk management competencies required of OTM graduates of polytechnics in Gombe State, Nigeria for electronic records management?

Null Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance;

1. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of administrative supervisors on the extent database management competencies are required of OTM graduates of polytechnics in Gombe State, Nigeria for electronic records management based on years of working experience (1-5years, 6-10 years and above 10 years).
2. There is no significant difference in the mean rating of administrative supervisors on the extent database management competencies are required of OTM graduates of polytechnics in Gombe State, Nigeria for electronic records management based on educational attainment (PhD/M.Sc./M.Ed. and B.Sc/B.Ed/HND).
3. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of administrative supervisors on the extent records risk management competencies are required of OTM graduates of polytechnics in Gombe State, Nigeria for electronic records management based on years of working experience (1-5years, 6-10 years and above 10 years).
4. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of administrative supervisors on the extent records risk management competencies are required of polytechnic OTM graduates of polytechnic in Gombe State, Nigeria for electronic records management based on educational attainment (PhD/M.Sc./M.Ed. and B.Sc/B.Ed/HND).

2. METHOD

The study adopted descriptive survey research design. The study was carried out in Gombe State, Nigeria. The population of this study consisted of 66 administrative supervisors in the two polytechnics in Gombe State, Nigeria. (Source: Academic Planning Units of the Polytechnics in Gombe State, Nigeria as at 25th March, 2023). The polytechnics are Federal Polytechnic Kaltungo, Gombe State with 34 administrative supervisors and Gombe State Polytechnic Bajoga with 32 administrative supervisors. There was no sampling since the population was manageable. A self-developed questionnaire titled "Database/risk Management Competencies Required for Electronic Records Management (DMC-RERM). The instrument was structured on a five-point rating scale of Very Highly Required (VHR), Highly Required (HR), Required (D), Lowly Required (LR), and Not Required.

The face validity of the instrument was established using the opinions of three experts, two experts in Business Education and one expert in Measurement and Evaluation. The reliability of the instrument was established using pilot-testing method and data collected were analyzed using Cronbach Alpha formula which yielded Coefficient values of .91 and .85 for clusters B1 to B2 respectively with an overall reliability value of .88. The researcher with the help of two research assistants

administered copies of the questionnaire to the respondents in their offices. On-the spot administration and collection method was adopted. Out of 66 copies of questionnaire distributed, 62 (94%) were correctly filled and returned. Descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions and determine the homogeneity or other wise of the respondents’ opinions. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) and t-test were used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 23.0. The decision rule was that a null hypothesis was rejected where the p- value was less than the significant value of .05; otherwise, the null hypothesis was accepted.

3. RESULTS

Research Question 1

To what extent are database management competencies required of OTM graduates of polytechnics in Gombe State, Nigeria for electronic records management.

Table 1: Respondents’ mean ratings on extent database management competencies are required of OTM graduates for electronic records management N = 62

S/N	Database Management Competencies	\bar{X}	SD	Remarks
1	Create and maintain data	4.59	.49	Very Highly Required
2	Extract and list all records	4.47	.52	Highly Required
3	Sort records in ascending or descending order	3.67	.47	Highly Required
4	Generate formulated text with title and subtitle	4.09	.51	Required
5	Create a record in a spread sheet	3.62	.52	Highly Required
6	Classify data into convenient groups	4.55	.50	Very Highly Required
7	Import data from excel markup language document	4.62	.61	Very Highly Required
8	Create report in reporting wizard	3.52	.84	Highly Required
9	Create records with design sheet view	3.51	.74	Highly Required
10	Migrate data into SharePoint,	4.50	.65	Very Highly Required
11	Relate data from different field	3.88	.49	Highly Required
12	Manage visual basic editor	3.73	.50	Highly Required
13	Get data from hypertext	3.83	.79	Highly Required
14	Create data base email	4.59	.51	Very Highly Required
15	Manipulate query wizard	4.47	.54	Highly Required
Cluster Mean		4.11		Highly Required

Data in Table 1 show that items 1, 6, 7, 10 and 14 are very highly required of OTM graduates for electronic records management with mean scores ranging from 4.55 to 4.59. Items 2, 3, 5, 8, 9, 11, 12, 13 and 15 with mean scores ranging between 3.52 to 4.47 are highly required while the remaining item is simply required. The cluster mean score of 4.11 shows that on the whole, database management competencies are highly required of OTM graduates of polytechnics in Gombe State, Nigeria for electronic records management. The standard deviation of .47 to .84 means that all the items are within the same range showing that the respondents are not wide apart in their ratings.

Research Question 2

To what extent are records risk management competencies required of OTM graduates of polytechnics in North East Nigeria for electronic records management?

Table 2: Respondents’ mean ratings on extent records risk management competencies are required of OTM graduates for electronic records management N = 62

S/N	Risk Management Competences	\bar{X}	SD	Remarks
16	Plans for records disaster prevention	4.50	.50	Very Highly Required
17	Apply records disaster recovery techniques	4.19	.49	Highly Required
18	Preserve the security and protection of all organizations’ records	3.66	.61	Highly Required
19	Identify and evaluate risk in records management	4.47	.59	Highly Required
20	Identify and develop risk mitigation techniques and strategies	4.43	.50	Highly Required
21	Document steps taken during the risk assessment process	4.54	.52	Very Highly Required
22	Develop emergency planning strategies	3.64	.48	Highly Required
23	Develop techniques for disaster recovery	3.58	.52	Highly Required
24	Coordinate disaster teams and explain teams’ responsibilities	3.71	.56	Highly Required
25	Apply the appropriate security classification to record	4.47	.50	Highly Required
Cluster Mean		4.12		Highly Required

Table 2 shows that items 16 and 21 with mean scores of 4.50 and 4.54 are risk management competencies very highly required of OTM graduates of polytechnics for electronic records management while the remaining eight items with mean scores ranging from 3.58 to 4.47 are rated highly required. The cluster mean score of 4.12 shows that on the whole, risk management competencies are highly required of OTM graduates of polytechnics in Gombe State, Nigeria for electronic records management. The standard deviation shows that there is homogeneity in the respondents’ responses.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of administrative supervisors on the extent database management competencies are required of OTM graduates of polytechnics in Gombe State, Nigeria for electronic records management based on years of working experience (1-5years, 6-10 years and above 10 years).

Table 3: Summary of one-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) on the ratings of administrative supervisors on database management competencies required of OTM graduates for electronic records management based on years of experience

Source of Variance	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	P-value	Decision
Between Groups	3084.55	2	1542.28	.972	.38	Not Significant
Within Groups	153938.29	363	1586.99			
Total	157022.84	366				

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Table 3 shows f-ratio of .97 at 2 and 363 degrees of freedom with a p-value of .38 is greater than the p-value of .05 (.38 >.05). The null hypothesis of no significant difference between the three groups is therefore accepted. This means that there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of administrative supervisors on the extent database management competencies are required of OTM graduates of polytechnics in Gombe State, Nigeria for electronic records management based on years of working experience.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference in the mean of administrative supervisors on the extent database management competencies are required of OTM graduates of polytechnics in the North East, Nigeria for electronic records management based on educational attainment (PhD/M.Sc./M.Ed. and B.Sc/B.Ed/HND).

Table 4: Summary of t-test analysis of mean ratings of administrative supervisors on the extent database management competencies are required of OTM graduates for records management based on educational attainment

Educational Attainment	N	\bar{X}	SD	df	t-value	P-value	Decision
PhD/M.Sc./M.Ed.	115	54.85	2.97	364	.72	.47	Not Significant
B.Sc/B.Ed/HND	251	53.92	2.98				

Table 4 shows that t - value of .72 at 364 degree of freedom with p-value of .47 is greater than the significant value of .05 (.47 >.05). The null hypothesis of no significant difference between the two groups is therefore accepted. This means that there is no significant difference in the mean of administrative supervisors on the extent database management competencies are required of OTM graduates of polytechnics in the North East, Nigeria for electronic records management based on educational attainment.

Hypothesis 3

There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of administrative supervisors on the extent records risk management competencies are required of OTM graduates of polytechnics in Gombe State, Nigeria for electronic records management based on years of working experience (1-5years, 6-10 years and above 10 years).

Table 5: Summary of one-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) on the ratings of administrative supervisors on records risk management competencies required of OTM graduates for electronic records management based on years of experience

Sources of Variance	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	P-value	Decision
Between Groups	3.88	2	1.93	.30	.741	Not Significant
Within Groups	622.33	363	6.42			
Total	626.19	366				

Table 5 shows f-ratio of .30 at 2 and 363 degrees of freedom with a p-value of .74 is greater than the p-value of .05 (.74 >.05). The null hypothesis of no significant difference between the three groups is therefore accepted. This means that there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of administrative supervisors on the extent records risk management competencies are required of OTM graduates of polytechnics in Gombe State, Nigeria for electronic records management based on years of working experience.

Hypothesis 4

There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of administrative supervisors on the extent records risk management competencies are required of polytechnic OTM graduates of polytechnic in Gombe State, Nigeria for electronic records management based on educational attainment (PhD/M.Sc./M.Ed. and B.Sc/B.Ed/HND).

Table 6: Summary of t-test analysis of mean ratings of administrative supervisors on the extent records risk management competencies are required of OTM graduates for records management based on educational attainment

Educational Attainment	N	\bar{X}	SD	df	t-value	P-value	Decision
PhD/M.Sc./M.Ed.	115	37.74	2.45	364	.11	.03	Significant
B.Sc/B.Ed/HND	251	34.49	1.57				

Table 6 shows that t - value of .11 at 364 degree of freedom with p-value of .03 is less than the significant value of .05 (.11 < .05). The null hypothesis of no significant difference between the two groups is therefore rejected. This means that there is a significant difference in the mean ratings of administrative supervisors on the extent records risk management competencies are required of polytechnic OTM graduates of polytechnic in Gombe State, Nigeria for electronic records management based on educational attainment.

4. DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Findings of the study showed that database management competencies were highly required of OTM graduates of polytechnics in Gombe State, Nigeria for electronic records management. This finding concurs with that of Ezenwa for and Garba (2020) that OTM graduate workers possess database management competencies at a moderate level and possess web page design competencies at a little level. Ovbiagele, Mgbonyebi and Olaniye (2019) revealed that OTM graduates required database management competencies for office e-records management in the e-records world of work for global competitiveness. In support, Egbunefu and Ubani (2019) asserted that database management competencies enhance administrative workers' productivity. According to Oguejio for and Umeh (2016), OTM graduates require database management skills to manage records electronically in the civil service. Findings of the study also revealed that there was no significant difference in the mean ratings of administrative supervisors on the extent database management competencies were required of OTM graduates of polytechnics in Gombe State, Nigeria for electronic records management based on years of working experience. According to Oketoobo, Lawal, and Onipede (2011), years of working experiences did not significantly influence respondents' perception on ICT competencies needed by graduates of business education (OTM graduates inclusive) for effective job performance.

It was also found that there was no significant difference in the mean rating of administrative supervisors on the extent database management competencies were required of OTM graduates of polytechnics in the Gombe State, Nigeria for electronic records management based on educational attainment. In other words, administrative supervisors in both groups agreed that OTM graduates require database management competencies for electronic records management.

Findings of the study also showed that risk management competencies were highly required of OTM graduates of polytechnics in Gombe State, Nigeria for electronic records management. The findings specifically revealed that risk management competencies such as abilities to plan for records disaster prevention, and document steps taken during the risk assessment process were highly required of OTM polytechnic graduates while such risk management competencies as abilities to; apply records disaster recovery techniques, preserve the security and protection of all organizations' records, identify and evaluate risk in records management, identify and develop risk mitigation techniques and strategies, and develop emergency planning strategies among others were highly required. In support of this view point, Crampton (2022) noted that records are one of the most valuable assets of tertiary institutions, and as a result, records managers need to have the ability to analyze risks involved in carrying out electronic records keeping. Dietrich (2017) also asserted that graduates of records management programme must possess risk management competencies to be able to carry out effective records risk analysis. Ngoepe (2014) reported that risk identification competencies are important for effective electronic records management. The findings further disclosed that there was no significant difference in the mean ratings of administrative supervisors on the extent records risk management competencies were required of OTM graduates of polytechnics in Gombe State, Nigeria for electronic records management based on years of working experience. However, it was discovered that administrative supervisors differed significantly in their mean ratings on the extent records risk management competencies were required of polytechnic OTM graduates of polytechnic in Gombe State, Nigeria for electronic records management based on educational attainment. Findings in respect to educational attainment is supported by earlier report of Sarwoko, Armanu and Hadiwidjojo (2013) which revealed that educational qualification was a significant factor affecting competencies possess by graduates of tertiary institutions.

5. CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study concluded that OTM graduates in polytechnics in Gombe State, Nigeria highly require database/riskmanagement competencies for effective management of the records in their institutions.

5.1. Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

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1. Administrators of Nigerian polytechnics should constantly retrain OTM graduates working in their institutions by providing in-service programmes such as workshops, seminars and conferences to enable them up-date their database and risks management competencies for effective records management.
2. Curriculum planners of OTM programme in the various polytechnics in Nigeria should review its contents to incorporate database/risk management competencies.
3. Government and other stakeholders should adequately provide modern technologies/facilities to all OTM departments in polytechnics in Nigeria to enable lecturers utilize them widely in equipping students with needed electronic records competencies for effective records management.

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